

NEWSLETTER

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Created by: TES2A & IGTP

SMA TB

Involving nine partners, from seven countries, SMA-TB mission is to generate a medical algorithm to stratify patients for predicting the course of the disease and its response to the intervention, to be applied during clinical management to improve and personalize TB treatment. Host-Directed Therapies (HDT) have been recently proposed to shorten treatment length and by to improve the patients' outcomes while not increasing the risk of generating drug resistance. One of our main objectives is providing TB patients with better quality of life and to develop a holistic approach to personalize medicine for TB and infectious disease.

During the first part of the SMA-TB project, and despite the COVID-19 outbreak, the project partners have been working together on setting up project tools, preparation of Clinical Trials, capacity building and SMA-TB communication and dissemination. 2021 will now be the time to start the Clinical Trials in South Africa and Georgia to collect all the samples and data for further research.

2020 has painfully shown us how necessary is the interdisciplinary research on infectious diseases, which makes our involvement in SMA-TB an additional opportunity to contribute to this global challenge. Therefore, we are very happy to welcome this first edition of the SMA-TB newsletter. The communication dimension is part of SMA-TB's integrated approach not only for sharing project's achievements, but also helping everyday lives of patients and their career and other responsible for TB. Our goal is to give information with transparency to all stakeholders' groups, by sharing current status and project's development. With this aim, I hope our newsletter will be useful for you to keep in touch and get involved.

Dr. Cristina Vilaplana, SMA-TB Project Coordinator

LAUNCH OF THE PROJECT: the Kick Off Meeting

Last February 3-5th, SMA-TB Project was launched. SMA-TB General Assembly, Scientific and Ethical Advisory Boards met together in Barcelona. IGTP, the project coordinator, organised the KoM in the Cultural Centre of the Casa-Palau Macaya, an architectural treasure of Catalan Modernism, thanks to the hospitality and collaboration of "la Caixa" Foundation. [>>Learn more](#)

Design Thinking Workshop

During the second day of KOM, 4th of February 2020, the Design Thinking Workshop focused on Emotional Burden of TB Disease was organised. The workshop, conducted by Prof. Miguel Ángel Heras, from ESADE Business School, was a perfect mean to approach the TB emotional burden problem in a holistic way, following so called “5-whys” methodology, and provided very interesting ideas which might be further exploited in SMA-TB communication and dissemination activities. Moreover, it resulted as an excellent team-building tool.

SMA-TB Website

The updated information about the SMA-TB project, together with the public deliverables, are available on the project website. SMA-TB website is designed as a dissemination and communication tool, providing information for healthcare professionals and researchers, as well as a tailored message for general public. If you want to know more about the SMA-TB consortium and project, as well as our contact details, please visit: <https://www.smatb.eu/>

Clinical Trial (CT) Set-up

Despite the impact of COVID outbreak with different intensities in the different countries within the consortium, SMA-TB partners have been working in the project in order to keep fighting against TB.

SMA-TB CT protocol, patient information leaflet and informed consents forms were submitted and approved by South African Regulatory Authority SAPHRA and University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg Human Research Ethics Committee for South African recruitment sites, Soweto and Matlosana. The protocol has been also submitted to the regulatory authority of Georgia, the Ministry of Internally Displaced Persons from the Occupied Territories, Labour, Health and Social Affairs of Georgia (MOH), and is pending of approval for the Georgian site, and to the Hospital Universitari Germans Trias i Pujol Ethics Committee in Badalona (Catalonia), as required by the EC.

CT e-consent

Following the decisions taken during the KoM, and aiming a better understanding of SMA-TB CT objectives and procedures, the SMA-TB consortium created, with the support of [Bicoté](#), a short video that will be used as the e-consent information tool for the clinical trial participants, as well as for anyone wanting to learn about the SMA-TB CT. You can watch the video [here](#). It explains in a very comprehensive way the rationale of SMA-TB concept, how the CT will be performed, what is expected from the patient, which are potential benefits, as well as side effects. The message is produced both in English and in Georgian.

Sites Capacity Package

In the last 3 months, sites capacity materials were generated including training documents, working procedures and workflow infographics. The CT set up involves ensuring that the sites have the necessary capacity to conduct it, in terms of equipment, homogenization of protocols and procedures and training of personnel (clinicians, researchers, nurses). In this context, IGTP organized regular meetings with the sites to better understand their needs and work accordingly.

From the more scientific point of view, 8 Standard Operation Procedures (SOPs) and the respective Protocol Workflow infographics were created.

SMA-TB Novel Stratified Medicine Algorithm to predict treatment responses to host-directed therapy in TB (SMA-TB)

Required material/reagents for sample processing - AT THE LAB

<p>Pipettes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Store and keep at RT. • Maintain in sterile conditions • Always open inside the flow chamber 		
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Mr. Frosty™ Cooler

- Store and keep the cooler at RT (18-25°C) while not in use.
- **Maintenance:** Fill with 250mL of isopropanol (stored at RT) as indicated on device's instructions of use. Change isopropanol solution for every 5 uses.
- **Tip!** mark with an adhesive tape every time the cooler is used.
- **Use:** Introduce each corresponding **cryotube** and incubate at -80°C overnight or during the weekend.
- **After volunteer visit:** once each corresponding **cryotube** is transferred to a **cryobox**, keep the cooler at RT until next usage.

Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS)

- Store FBS bottles at -20°C and avoid repeated freeze-thaw cycles.
- **Maintenance:** Heat-inactivate and prepare ready-to-use aliquots as described in **SMA-TB SOP01 - Preparation of PMBCs freezing solutions**.
- **Use:** Prepare all the FBS aliquots needed before starting patient recruitment and keep at -20°C.

Procedure for Plasma and PBMCs Collection

- ① **Blood collection to CPT tubes**
Collect the blood into 2x CPT tube. Fill the tube with blood until reaching the blue line.
Gently invert the CPT tubes 8-10x.
- ② **Plasma and PBMCs separation**
Centrifuge the CPT tubes at RT (18-25°C) for 30' at 1600g.

Most of this documentation will be public so that third parties can use them. If you are interested in knowing which tools are available to be shared, please contact us.

SMA-TB Training

SMA-TB project has performed training in Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) a secure web application for building and managing online surveys and databases.

One of most important components in capacity building process is to train the staff in using developed tools and protocols in the most efficient and professional way. During the first year, SMA-TB team developed specific training kits, supporting documentation, and has conducted training activities aiming to prepare staff for SMA-TB CT in South Africa.

Training sessions have been recorded, aiming to use this audio-visual tool for the future training sessions for SMA-TB CT in Georgia.

Most of these documents will be public so that third parties can use them. If you are interested, please contact us.

Joint activities & Other projects

Our mission is to make the best use of EC funds, by not only generating new insights and the most advanced host directed therapies, but also through sharing knowledge and collaboration with consortia and related projects. The scientific leaders of DRTB-HDT project (GA No. 847465), prof. Robert S. Wallis from the Aurum Institute (South Africa) and, Dr. José Domínguez and Team from INNOVA4TB project (GA No. 823854) attended the SMA-TB KoM meeting, so we discussed in detail future cooperation taking an advantage of synergy and complementarity between these two H2020 projects. Also, at the beginning of the project the joint press release was done with MISTRAL H2020 project (GA No. 847943), focused on HDT applied to AIDS, led by IRSICAixa, PI: Roger Paredes, and funded within the same call.

We have developed a tool that other projects could use to monitor their impacts. So, if you want to know more about it, contact us.

SMA-TB Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

SMA-TB project has defined 26 KPIs that are used to monitor the progress of the project, to detect and to correct any problem during the project execution, aiming transparency and stakeholders' engagement. Please find here below current status of each KPI.

KPI n	NAME	Target	Current Status
KPI-1	Cycle time from IRB submit to IRB approval (in days)	160	105 days (in South Africa)
KPI-2	Time from Open to enrolment until the enrolment quota is met (in months)	30	N/A Enrolment hasn't started yet
KPI-3	Trial retention	85%	
KPI-4	Prevalence of functional impairment	1,5 months	
KPI-5	N of HQoL questionnaires completed	711	
KPI-6	Capacity Building tools kit	1	
KPI-7	N of relevant biomarkers	3-5	N/A
KPI-8	Clinical and analytical validation of CD5L kit	1	N/A
KPI-9	Key enclaves linked to response to intervention	3-5	N/A
KPI-10	Medical algorithm for patients' stratification	1	N/A
KPI-11	Open-access publication counts	5	No publications yet
KPI-12	Citation Impact	10	
KPI-13	Co-authored analysis	20%	
KPI-14	N of dissemination activities	5	4
KPI-15	N of communication activities	12	9
KPI-16	Media citation analysis	1500	Twitter impressions = 40,855 Website total site sessions = 555
KPI-17	Stakeholders' rep on SMA-TB gov bodies, committees & meetings	4	8
KPI-18	Meetings with policy makers	6	0

KPI n	NAME	Target	Current Status
KPI-19	Resources devoted to stakeholder engagement	11,500€/y	485.07€
KPI-20	Timelines in D and M submission	<15% delay	4% for D, 36% for M
KPI-21	N management meetings conducted/planned	100%	100%
KPI-22	Interactions with EAB	yearly	100%
KPI-23	Gender population in CT	50%	N/A- Enrolment hasn't started yet
KPI-24	% Promoted, recruited, and retained personnel and costs	20%	12%
KPI-25	Gender dimension (participants)	50%	72% females / 28% men
KPI-26	Education (education degrees and associated costs/y)	15	32

If you are interested in knowing more about the SMA-TB project or want to collaborate, please do not hesitate to contact us:

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<https://www.smatb.eu/>

@smatbproject

SMA-TB

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